

HARNESSING GREEN ENERGY FOR ENHANCED VALUE: EMPIRICAL INSIGHTS FROM NIGERIA'S LISTED INDUSTRIAL GOODS FIRMS

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Abstract

Rising energy costs, which harmfully affect the environment in areas where firms are located, have raised growing concerns, thereby increasing interest in green energy as a viable alternative to reduce environmental degradation, greenhouse gas emissions, and over-dependence on fossil fuel-based energy sources. Against the backdrop of rising energy costs, environmental concerns, and increasing investor attention to sustainability, this study harnesses green energy to enhance value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The study employed a non-survey research design, using a sample size of nine (9) industrial goods firms from a total population of thirteen (13) that were listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) group, with data extracted from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms for a period of 15 years (2010–2024). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics to provide a summary of the variables, and correlation analysis was performed using the Pearson correlation technique. The multiple regression results demonstrate that EE and GER significantly influence the value of the selected industrial goods firms in Nigeria, while the ECRR has an insignificant impact on firm value. Therefore, the study concludes that improvements in firm value among listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria are driven more by strategic investments in green energy efficiency and the adoption of green energy sources than by short-term energy cost considerations. Consequently, the study recommends that the management of the sampled listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria prioritize strategic investments in energy-efficient technologies and production processes, as improvements in energy efficiency have been shown to enhance firm value. The adoption and integration of green energy sources into their energy mix must be increased to reduce environmental risks, improve operational sustainability, and strengthen market valuation. In addition, by investing in clean, efficient energy systems that promote sustainable industrial growth and long-term firm value, management should align their energy efficiency and green energy initiatives with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030, particularly SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

Keywords: Green energy efficiency, value, listed industrial goods firm in Nigeria

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Over the years, managers, investors, researchers, and financial analysts have estimated a firm's value based on different financial indices. Maximizing firm value eventually has been every firm's primary objective. The concern is whether a firm is undervalued, fairly valued, or overvalued based, on financial performance and the market price of shares. According to Sucuahi and Cambarihan (2016), industrial establishments' wealth, technology, organizational structure, human resources, discounted cash flow, and environmental factors determine the extent to which a firm is valued. In addition, Madwe et al. (2025) considered energy efficiency, such as the use of technology and practices to reduce energy consumption without sacrificing performance or comfort (e.g., better insulation, LED lights, and fuel-efficient cars), as a

determinant of firm valuation. Meanwhile, the activities of lowering sources that naturally replenish and have minimal environmental impact, such as solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal, refers to green renewable energy or green energy efficiency.

In Nigeria, green energy has evolved from a secondary choice to a critical national essential, defined by the invention of power from indigenous, renewable, and low-emission sources such as wind, hydro, solar, and biomass. According to Eleri and Onuvae (2022), the adoption of green energy as an alternative change is driven by the pressing need to address the nation's unceasing energy poverty, reduce reliance on volatile fossil fuel exports and polluting petrol/diesel generators, and adhere to global climate commitments such as the 2060 Net-Zero pledge. The Nigerian Energy Transition Plan (ETP) explicitly positions green energy as the cornerstone for achieving universal energy access, economic development, and climate resilience, highlighting abundant resources such as solar irradiation across the country as vital for decentralized power solutions (Federal Government of Nigeria, 2022). Therefore, in Nigerian discourse, green energy is not merely an environmental concern but a multifaceted tool for energy security, job creation, and sustainable industrialization.

Organizations that adopt green energy as an efficiency strategy to generate financial benefits accept the strategies with the aim of lowering energy costs, enhancing corporate competitiveness, improving the company's reputation, and complying with stakeholder demands for firm environmental responsibility (Garcia-Quevedo et al., 2021). The current global transition toward sustainable energy systems has intensified discussions on the economic implications of voluntarily adopting green energy for firms. In developing economies such as Nigeria, where energy inefficiency and reliance on fossil fuels remain prevalent, the adoption of green energy technologies has become both a strategic and regulatory imperative.

Over the years, Nigeria industrial goods sector, which contributes significantly to economic output and employment, faces persistent challenges related to high energy costs, unstable power supply, and environmental degradation. The high levels of energy consumption in these firms emanate from these sectors' high levels. These challenges have heightened the relevance of green energy solutions as a means of improving operational efficiency and long-term firm value. This implies that the value of a firm's stock is determined by all relevant information, including financial and non-financial issues that can be used to assess a firm's sustainable growth.

Management's efficiency in green energy adoption serves as a bridge between firms value increases or decreases, which is the concern of management and stakeholders, since providing financial and non-financial information related to the use of green energy for the day-to-day to running of the business. The full adoption of green energy can enhance a firm's reputation, value profitability, financial performance, and long-term investment attractiveness. Efficiency in green energy has shown a positive trend in recent years by scholars from both developing and developed economies (Dopierala et al., 2022; Hulshof & Mulder, 2020; Madwe et al., 2025). However, other findings show that green energy efficiency positively influences firm value (Li et al., 2017; Lin et al., 2019; Issa & Hanayska, 2023). This indicates that firms that invest in sustainable practices, such as green energy, are financially beneficial eventually. Empirical evidence on the benefits associated with green energy efficiency is increasingly critical, , but empirical evidence on

whether green energy efficiency generates financial returns in Nigeria, especially in listed industrial goods firms, is limited.

The core objective of corporate management for listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria is value maximization. These firms are listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group, where shareholder wealth considerations are paramount. Investors increasingly incorporate environmental performance and sustainability indicators into their decisions. Firms that invest in renewable energy, energy-efficient technologies, and emission-reduction practices may enjoy reputational benefits, cost savings, and improved access to capital (Madwe et al., 2025). Despite this growing relevance, empirical evidence on the value implications of GE efficiency within Nigeria's industrial sector remains limited. Methodologically, many prior studies have relied on short timeframes, small sample sizes, or descriptive analysis that limits the generalizability of findings (Lin et al., 2019; Issa & Hanayska, 2023). Moreover, there is a lack of studies that apply GMM panel regression techniques for the analysis. This gap provides a methodological opportunity to employ robust econometric approaches that capture firm-specific effects over time. Therefore, this research seeks to fill these practical, empirical, and methodological gaps by examining the influence of green energy efficiency on value among listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria, offering new insights into how green energy efficiency adoption may drive corporate success in a diverse cultural and regulatory environment in a developing economy like Nigeria. Therefore, the following objectives are proposed:

- i. Assess the impact of energy efficiency on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Evaluates the impact of energy cost to revenue on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.
- iii. Examines the impact of green energy on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

This study is further structured into five sections. Section 2 outlines the literature review and conceptual framework. Section 3 presents the methodological aspects of the materials, including the data and model specifications. Section 4 presents the results and a discussion, and Section 5 presents the conclusions and recommendations of this study.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Firm Value Concept

According to the shareholder's approach, a firm's primary objective is value maximization for shareholders (Friedman, 1970). This means the maximization of a firm's equity, which is this value of expected cash flows that shareholders expect from the firm. Thus, maximizing a firm's value is feasible only when scheduled benefits, such as revenue growth and profitability, are maximized eventually (Stubelj, 2010). According to Christiawan and Tarin (2007), measures of value include nominal, market, intrinsic, book, and liquidation value. They note that the most representative concept for determining market performance is intrinsic value, which and, however, is very difficult to estimate. The difficulty is that the determination of intrinsic value requires the ability to identify significant variables that determine the firm's market performance which vary among firms (Moeljadi, 2014).

Brigham et al. (1999) defined value as the benefits that accrue to the management of financial markets and corporate organizations as they continue to grow. According to this definition, value constitutes market perceptions of a firm's performance and its ability to sustain investment growth. It is an economic term used to describe a business organization's worth at a given point in time. Theoretically, it is the

amount payable if an entity is to be bought or taken over. Thus, determining firm value, similar to that of an asset, is based on either book value or market value. Generally, firm value refers to the firm's market value (Wahyudi & Prawesti, 2006). This means that the interest of investors is often in the return that accrues to investments in the form of embedded capital gains and dividends; hence, the higher the return to shareholders, the higher the market value of their shares (Qomariah, 2015). Different indices can be used to determine the value of a firm can be determined. James Tobin of Yale University popularizes Tobin's Q quotient. As a Nobel laureate in economics, Tobin hypothesizes that combining the market value of all companies on the stock market should equal their replacement costs. For this study, firm value was proxied by Tobin's Q.

Green Energy Efficiency Concept

Green energy refers to energy generated from renewable and environmentally friendly sources, such as solar, wind, biomass, and hydropower. Green energy, often used interchangeably with renewable energy, refers to energy generated from natural, replenishable sources that have a minimal negative impact on the environment throughout their lifecycle (Eleri & Onuvae, 2022). Unlike fossil fuels, these sources, including solar, wind, geothermal, hydro, and sustainably sourced biomass, produce little to no greenhouse gas emissions or air pollutants during operation (Irena, 2023). The core principle of green energy extends beyond mere renewability to encompass broader sustainability goals, such as mitigating climate change, reducing ecological degradation, and fostering energy security. As defined by the United Nations, sustainable development and the transition to a low-carbon economy are fundamental to meet current energy needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs (UN, 2022). Therefore, the concept is inherently linked to a systemic shift in energy production toward both ecologically benign and perpetually available sources.

Energy efficiency, on the other hand, relates to the use of less energy to produce the same level of output. Therefore, green energy efficiency combines the adoption of renewable energy sources with efficient energy use to minimize environmental impact and operational waste. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA) and recent empirical studies, energy efficiency entails reducing waste in energy conversion, transmission, and end use, thereby enhancing sustainability, lowering costs, and reducing GHG emissions without undermining productivity (Liu et al., cited in *Frontiers in Environmental Science*). It addresses the profound inefficiencies that characterize the national energy landscape, from high technical and commercial losses in the grid to the widespread use of inefficient appliances and energy-intensive industrial processes (Onyeji, 2023). In practice, this involves deploying demand-side management technologies such as smart meters, promoting the adoption of high-efficiency appliances (e.g., LED lighting and inverter ACs), and retrofitting buildings and industries to reduce their energy intensity, thereby lowering costs and emissions. For a nation where supply consistently falls short of demand, energy efficiency is recognized as the "first fuel" it reduces the required capacity of generation, making it cheaper and faster to meet power needs with green energy sources (Sambo & Garba, 2021). Therefore, in the context of green energy, efficiency not only refers to reducing the energy required to produce goods and services but also to improving the integration and performance of renewable energy technologies, such as smart grids, energy storage, and low-loss distribution systems that support cleaner

energy supply chains (Akinbola & Okafor, 2023). Firms that install such technologies and practices can achieve higher output with lower energy inputs, advancing both environmental and economic goals.

Underpinning Theories

Several theories explain the relationship between green energy efficiency and firm value. These include stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984) and resource-based view theory (Barney, 1991). Freeman propounded the stakeholder theory in 1984. This theory posits that firms create value by effectively managing relationships with all stakeholders, including shareholders, employees, customers, regulators, host communities, and the environment (Freeman, 1984). From this perspective, green energy efficiency represents a strategic response to the growing environmental expectations of key stakeholders. Firms, particularly industrial good firms, can reduce their energy consumption, emissions, and environmental footprints, demonstrating accountability and responsiveness to environmental concerns. This proactive stance helps firms mitigate regulatory risks, avoid environmental sanctions, and enhance corporate legitimacy, thereby strengthening stakeholder trust and support. Fama and Jensen (1983) further argued that effective governance mechanisms align managerial actions with stakeholder interests, suggesting that green energy efficiency investments can reduce agency conflicts and contribute to long-term firm value. According to Chien (2022), enhancing energy efficiency is fundamental for achieving sustainable development goals and improving firm value.

Stakeholder theory concludes that firms that internalize environmental responsibilities can gain reputational advantages that translate into improved financial outcomes (Madwe et al., 2025). In energy-intensive industries, stakeholders increasingly reward firms that adopt cleaner and more efficient energy practices through favorable investment decisions, customer loyalty, and reduced cost of capital. Empirical studies have shown that environmentally responsible behavior, including energy efficiency initiatives, enhances firm valuation by improving market perceptions and long-term sustainability prospects (Madwe et al., 2025 and Eccles et al., 2014). Consequently, green energy efficiency serves as a mechanism through which firms align economic objectives with stakeholder expectations, reinforcing firm value within a stakeholder-oriented governance framework. Hence, this study employed stakeholder theory to examine how stakeholders' demands influence the relationship between green energy efficiency and firm value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

The RBV theory was propounded by Barney in 1991. The theory argues that firms achieve sustained competitive advantage and superior performance by acquiring and effectively deploying valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable resources (Barney, 1991). Green energy efficiency is a strategic capability embedded in a firm's operational processes, technological know-how, and managerial expertise. Investments in energy-efficient technologies, renewable integration, and energy management systems enhance operational efficiency and reduce production costs for listed industrial good firms. Once developed, these capabilities; are difficult for competitors to replicate due to high capital requirements, technical complexity, and firm-specific learning, thereby positioning green energy efficiency as a source of competitive advantage that enhances firm value. Green energy capabilities can constitute valuable, rare, and inimitable resources that enhance competitive advantage and firm value.

Furthermore, RBV emphasizes that intangible assets, such as environmental management competencies, innovation capacity, and organizational culture, play a critical role in value creation. Green energy

efficiency reflects a firm's ability to continuously optimize resource utilization and adapt to environmental and regulatory pressures. Previous studies have suggested that firms with strong environmental capabilities outperform peers financially because they convert sustainability initiatives into cost savings, risk reduction, and innovation outcomes (Hart, 1995; Russo & Fouts, 1997). In this context, GEE is not merely a compliance activity but a strategic resource that strengthens firm resilience, improves profitability, and ultimately increases firm value over the long term. This study adopted the RBV theory to explain the impact of green energy efficiency and firm value because energy efficiency technologies are the resources that are employed to reduce production costs (energy costs), enhance production efficiency, and reflect commitment to environmentally responsible activities through available green or renewable energy (such as solar, wind, hydro, and geothermal), thereby improving firm reputation and investor confidence (Sun et al., 2024).

Development of Hypotheses from Empirical Studies

Green energy adoption, which may lead to organizational efficiency by firms in both the production and services sectors, is essential for reducing global warming, attaining energy independence, and building a sustainable future by shifting away from polluting energy sources. Previous empirical studies on the influence of green energy practices on firm value from both local and international sources documented mixed findings on the subject matter. For example, Madwe et al. (2025) assessed how energy efficiency influences the financial performance of the major higher polluters and emitters listed on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE). The study covered a period of 9 years (2015-2023). The population in South Africa consists of only higher polluters and emitter firms. Meanwhile, 58 companies listed on the JSE represent the sample size from the total population listed on the JSE. Data were sourced from the firm's annual financial reports for the period under study. The result from a two-step system generalized method of moments (SGMM) shows that energy efficiency (energy-saving strategies) does not influence the sampled firms' financial performance. The study was conducted outside Nigeria. Hence, the findings may not be the same in the Nigerian context given the differences in regulations.

Moreover, Dopierala et al. (2022) explored, who explored the impact of the adoption of energy efficiency on the firm performance of companies in the Baltic Sea Region. The multiple regression results show that the relationship between energy efficiency adoption and firm performance is insignificant. Marti-Ballester (2017), Hulshof and Mulder (2020), and Correia et al. (2021) also reported that the impact of EE on financial performance is insignificant. On the other hand, Li et al. (2017) surveyed the relationship between energy intensity and the performance of firms in the United States, while Lin et al. (2019) assessed the relationship between energy intensity and the performance of 400 Thai firms. Issa and Hanayska (2023) studied the impact of renewable energy on financial performance using non-financial companies in Europe.

The above studies documented a significant impact of green energy efficiency on the performance of the sampled firms under study. Hence, there is limited consensus on the causal influence of green energy efficiency on firm value, and several research gaps persist in this domain, especially at the international level. First, there is a dearth of local-level studies that assess the association between green energy efficiency firm values. However, different results could be obtained if a similar study is conducted in Nigeria due to differences in the ecology system and laws. Second, some studies covered periods of less

than 10 years, which may not give valid and robust results. It is noteworthy that green energy efficiency can positively impact firm value; however, the pathway through which this occurs has not been adequately explored in the existing literature at the local level (Nigeria) using industrial goods firms. However, different results could be obtained if a similar study is conducted in Nigeria due to differences in regulatory systems. As a result of the mixed findings, this study hypothesizes the following: H0₁: Energy efficiency has an insignificant impact on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. H0₂: Holding other factors constant, energy cost of revenue has an insignificant impact on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

H0₃: Ceteris paribus, green energy has an insignificant impact on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Figure 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study with a visual diagram showing how green energy efficiency proxies influence firm value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria based on the three hypotheses described above.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework of the study

A conceptual framework is a schematic presentation of the variables under investigation. The diagram in this study shows how green energy efficiency affects firm value, while leverage, firm age, and size were used as control variables.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A correlational research design was employed for the study as used by Issa and Hanayska (2023) and Madwe et al. (2025), since it relies on secondary data extracted from the annual reports and accounts of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. This design is chosen because the information on all the variables

of the study (green energy, firm value and control variables, leverage, firm age, and firm size) can be best obtained from the selected industrial goods firms' annual reports and accounts for the period under investigation. The study considered this design adequate for determining the impact of green energy on the value of the sampled firms. The research design is used when the goal is to establish the cause and effect of the relationship using quantitative data over a period of fifteen (15) years (2010-2024). Likewise, green energy and firm value have a wide range of theories under which this study is hinged.

Population of the study

The study population comprises all the 14 listed industrial goods firms on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of December 31 2024. At the time the study was conducted, there were 13 listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria (Table 1).

Table 1: Industrial Goods Firms Listed on NGX

S/No.	Names	Date of listing	Date Incorporated
1	Austin Laz & Company Inc.	2010	1982
2	Berger Paints Plc.	1967	1959
3	Beta Glass Plc.	1986	1974
4	Bua Cement Plc.	2020	2014
5	Cap Plc.	1978	1965
6	Cutix Plc.	1987	1982
7	Dangote Cement Company	2010	1992
8	Greif Nigeria Plc.	1979	1940
9	Lafarge Africa Plc.	1979	1959
10	Meyer Plc.	1979	1960
11	Notore Chemical Industrial Plc.	2018	2005
12	Premier Paints Plc.	1995	1982
13	Tripple Gee and Company Plc.	1980	1970

Source: NGX website, 2024

Given the nature and time frame of the study; it was necessary to select industrial goods firms that could provide reliable data. Firms that were not listed throughout the study period and without complete data were excluded.

Table 2: Study sample size

Sample Method	No.	No.
Firm listed on NGX as of December 31, 2024		13
Less:		
Listed after 2012 period	(2)	
Firms delisted during the period	(0)	
Firms without complete data	<u>(2)</u>	
Number of firms excluded		<u>(4)</u>
Firms included in the final sample		09
Number of years		<u>15</u>
Firm-year observations		<u>135</u>

Source: Generated from Table 1.

Data Analysis Techniques

This study used two main methods to analyze the data: descriptive statistics and correlation matrix, which served as a mechanism to check the association between independent and dependent variables and among independent variables. Furthermore, multiple regressions were adopted to empirically assess the impact of GE efficiency on firm value. Hence, the multiple regression technique models are specified as follows:

$$TQ = f(\text{GEE, the LEV FAGE, and FS}) \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

The above mentioned model is the functional relationship of the variables.

The next model is used to study how GE efficiency affects firm value:

$$TQ_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 EE_{it} + \beta_2 ECRR_{it} + \beta_3 GER_{it} + \beta_4 LEV_{it} + \beta_5 FAGE_{it} + \beta_6 FS_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where:

TQ_{it} = Tobin’s Q of firm “i” in period “t”

EE_{it} = Energy efficiency of firm “i” in period “t”

$ECRR_{it}$ = Energy cost of revenue ratio of firm “i” in period “t”

GER_{it} = Green energy ratio of firm “i” in period “t”

LEV_{it} = Leverage of firm “i” in period “t”

$FAGE_{it}$ = Age of firm “i” in period “t”

FS_{it} = Firm size of firm “i” in period “t”

β_0 = Intercept or constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_6$ = Regression coefficient of the explanatory variables

i = Firms

t = Period

ϵ = Error term of firm “i” in period “t”

Table 3 presents the variables’ description and measurement.

Table 3: Study variables and their measurements

Variables	Proxies	Nature	Symbol	Measurement	Source/Justification
Firm Value	Tobin’s Q	DV	TQ	Book value of debt + market value of equity/total assets.	Madwe et al. (2025), Sitompul et al. (2024), Widarwati et al. (2024), Kurniantaa and Dianawati (2020), and Fanet al. (2017).
Green energy efficiency	Energy Efficiency	IV	EE	Total energy consumed divided by total revenue.	Hulshof and Mulder (2020), Moon and Min (2020), Fanet al. (2017), and Zhang (2016).
	Energy cost of revenue ratio	IV	ECRR	Total energy cost divided by total revenue.	Madwe et al. (2025), Meiryani et al. (2023), Moon and Min (2020), and Zhang (2016).

	Green energy ratio	IV	GER	Renewable energy consumption divided by the total energy consumption	Meiryani et al. (2023), Hulshof and Mulder (2020), and Zhang (2016).
Leverage	Leverage	CV	The LEV	Total debt divided by total assets.	Madwe et al. (2025), Hulshof and Mulder (2020), and Moon and Min (2020).
Firm Age	Firm Age	CV	FAGE	Number of years since the firm was incorporated in Nigeria.	Olanisebe et al. (2026) and Madwe et al. (2025).
Firm Size	Firm Size	CV	FS	Natural logarithm of the total assets.	Madwe et al. (2025), Widarwati et al. (2024), and Kurniantaa and Dianawati (2020).

Source: Generated by the Researchers 2026.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

In this section, the data collected for the study are described and discussed. The descriptive statistics of the collected data are summarized in Table 4 as follows:

Table 4: Descriptive statistics of the variables

Variables	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
TQ	135	2.2318	3.6745	0.1044	6.0474
EE	135	0.1787	0.1458	0.0138	0.7940
ECRR	135	0.0320	0.0738	0	0.2712
GER	135	0.1112	0.1992	0	0.8498
The LEV	135	0.4246	0.1988	0.0004	0.8730
FAGE	135	33.8889	11.8048	0	57
FS	135	10.1208	1.0499	8.9710	12.7156

Source: STATA Output 14.0 Based on Data Generated from Sampled Firms (2010-2024).

The average TQ was 2.2318, with a standard deviation of 3.6745, indicating no limited dispersion or variation. The minimum and maximum firm value is 0.1044 and 6.0474, respectively. EE has a mean value of 0.1787 with a standard deviation of 0.1458, indicating a moderate variation in the level of EE across the sampled industrial goods firms. The minimum and maximum values of 0.0138 and 0.7940, respectively, this implies that while some firms operate with very low energy efficiency, others demonstrate high efficiency levels. This variation implies that industrial goods firms in Nigeria have differing of commitment to efficient energy use and operational optimization.

Furthermore, the ECRR has a mean value of 0.0320 with a standard deviation of 0.0738, indicating that, on average, energy costs constitute a small proportion of firms' revenue. The minimum value of zero and maximum value of 0.2712 suggest that while some firms incur negligible energy costs relative to revenue,

others experience higher energy cost burdens. The observed dispersion reflects differences in production processes, energy sourcing, and cost management practices across firms. Green Energy Ratio (GER) reports a mean value of 0.1112 and a standard deviation of 0.1992, indicating a generally low but widely dispersed adoption of green energy among the sampled firms. The minimum value of zero implies that some firms do not use green energy at all, while the maximum value of 0.8498 indicates substantial reliance on green energy by a few firms. This wide variation highlights the uneven integration of renewable and cleaner energy sources within Nigeria's IGS

Similarly, financial has a mean value of 0.4246 (42%) with a standard deviation of 0.1988 (20%), indicating that approximately 42% of firms' assets are financed through debt. The minimum and maximum values of 0.0004 and 0.8730, respectively, indicate considerable differences in capital structure across the industrial firms under study, ranging from almost debt-free to highly leveraged. This variation reflects the differing financing strategies and risk preferences of the sampled firms. Firm age (FAGE) shows a mean value of 34 years with a standard deviation of 12 years, indicating that the sampled IGFs are generally mature but vary in terms of operational longevity. The minimum value of zero, implies that the inclusion of young firms, whereas the maximum value of 57 years reflects the presence of long-established firms. This dispersion implies differences in firms' experience, market presence, and institutional maturity. FS had a mean, minimum, and maximum value of 10.1208, 8.9710, and 12.7156, respectively.

Correlation Analysis

Before proceeding to multivariate regression analysis, the pairwise correlations among the study variables should be examined. The correlation matrix offers insights into the direction and strength of linear relationships between variables and provides an initial check for potential multicollinearity, which could distort regression coefficient estimation and interpretation. Table 4 shows the correlations among the study variables.

Table 4: Correlation matrix

Variable	TQ	EVS	SOS	GVS	BGD	FS	MO	VIF
s								
TQ	1.0000							
EE	-0.1772	1.0000						1.98
ECRR	0.0401	0.3900	1.0000					1.69
GER	-0.2130	0.5876	0.5313	1.0000				2.00
The LEV	-0.4503	0.1986	-0.2328	0.0551	1.0000			1.22
FAGE	0.0707	0.2603	-0.0525	-0.1005	0.0827	1.0000		1.56
FS	-0.2915	0.3825	-0.2321	-0.1674	-0.1470	-0.5103	1.0000	1.59

Source: STATA Output 14.0 Based on Data Generated from Sampled Firms (2010-2024).

The correlation analysis results displayed in Table 4 indicates a positive relationship, suggesting that both the dependent and independent variables tend to increase together. This indicates that ECRR and FAGE positively correlate with TQ. Conversely, EE, GER, the LEV, and FS have a negative association with TQ. Meanwhile, most correlation coefficients are below the conventional threshold of 0.7, suggesting the

absence of a serious multicollinearity problem among the explanatory variables. This assessment was further validated using Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) analysis with the highest VIF observed at 2.00, which is below the accepted cut-off of 10.0 (Chatterjee & Hadi, 2015). Therefore, this study concludes that multicollinearity is not present in our model.

Regression Results

a) Impact of green energy efficiency on firm value

Table 5 presents the impact of green energy efficiency on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 5: Impact of green energy efficiency on firm value

Random effect (RE)			
	Coef.	Z	P>/z/
EE	-1.7693	-2.34	0.019
ECRR	-3.6909	-1.91	0.126
GER	-3.4968	-5.05	0.000
The LEV	-6.0473	-9.74	0.000
FAGE	-0.0361	-4.34	0.000
FS	-1.4168	-9.19	0.000
_CONS.	20.9535	11.33	0.000
R-Squared: Within	0.3010		
Between	0.1203		
Overall	0.1650		
Number of Obs.	135		
Number of groups	9		
Time periods	15		
Wald chi2(5)	219.76		
Prob> chi ²	0.0000		
Heteroskedasticity	0.0000		
Hausman Test - Prob>chi ²	0.1391		
The Lagrangian multiplier test for random effects, Prob> chibar ² = 0.0000			

Source: Stata Output Version 14.0

The overall result of the model is statistically significant, as shown by the Wald chi-square value of 219.76 with a probability value of 0.000, indicating that the explanatory variables jointly influence the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The R-squared values reveal that the model explains 17% of within-firm variation in firm value using TQ. The heteroskedasticity test result (p = 0.0000) confirms the presence of heteroskedasticity, which was corrected by robustness. Additionally, the results of the Hausman test (Prob> chi² = 0.1391) support the appropriateness of the random effects model, whereas the significant Lagrangian multiplier test confirms the presence of panel effects in the data. The results in Table 5 show a significant negative impact of energy efficiency on firm value with coefficients of -1.7693 and p-value of 0.019. This means that an increase in green energy efficiency measures leads to a decrease in firm value because of initial costs associated with green energy acquisition, indicating

that short-term costs of efficiency investments exceed financial benefits in the context of the study. This result agrees with those of Madwe et al. (2025) and Ruggiero and Lehtonene (2017).

However, the ECRR exhibits a negative but statistically insignificant relationship with the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The coefficient of 3.6909 and p-value of 0.126 indicate that the ratio of energy cost to revenue does not significantly affect firm value during the period under review. This suggests that investments in energy efficiency, while potentially reducing the ECRR, do not impose a material financial burden on firm value, as the proportion of energy costs to revenue remains too low or variable to drive meaningful valuation changes in Nigeria's industrial goods firms, where energy expenses often represent a minor operational component amid broader cost pressures such as raw materials and labor. This result is consistent with those of Sitompul et al. (2024), Dopierala et al. (2022), Hulshof and Mulder (2020), Correia et al. (2021), and Marti-Ballester (2017).

Meanwhile, Table 5 demonstrates a negative relationship between GER and firm value of listed sampled size, as proven statistically with the coefficient of -3.4968 with p-value 0.000. This means that when firms increase their proportion of green energy usage relative to total energy consumption, firm value rises by 3.4968 units, which is highly significant at the 1% level ($p < 0.01$), indicating that Nigeria's industrial goods sector's greater reliance on renewable or green sustainable energy sources enhances valuation through cost stability, regulatory compliance, and market appeal. The developed hypotheses of the study can now either be rejected or are not rejected from the results investor's perspective, this implies that investors are currently discounting firm value in response to higher GER, likely perceiving the associated capital expenditures and operational shifts as a net present cost outweighing the long-term benefits, or viewing such investments as misallocated capital in a constrained financial environment. This result agrees with those of Arslan and Islamoglu (2025), Madwe et al. (2025), and Ruggiero and Lehtonene (2017). For the control variables, the results showed that leverage, firm age, and size have a significant impact on the value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria.

Test of the Hypotheses

The developed hypotheses of the study can now either be rejected or are not rejected from the results. Table 6 summarizes the test of the hypothesis.

Table 6: Summary of the tested hypotheses

Hypotheses		Coef.	Z	P>/z/	Decision
EE → TQ	1	-1.7693	-2.34	0.019	Reject
ECRR → TQ	2	-3.6909	-1.91	0.126	Fail to reject
GER → TQ	3	-3.4968	-5.05	0.000	Reject

Source: Researcher's Compilation, 2026

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study explored the impact of green energy efficiency value of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria. The population is made up of 13 listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria as of 31st December 2024, out of which nine (9) listed industrial goods firms represented the sample size after applying two criteria. The study covers a period of 15 years from 2010 to 2024, while secondary data were obtained from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firm for the study period. The multiple regression results

demonstrate that EE and GER significantly influence the value of the selected industrial goods firms in Nigeria, while the ECRR has an insignificant impact on firm value. The inclusion of these variables in the model indicates that firm value is more responsive to operational and strategic improvements in energy use and the adoption of cleaner energy sources than to short-term energy cost fluctuations. This suggests that investors and the market place greater weight on firms' long-term efficiency gains and commitment to sustainable energy practices, which enhance competitiveness, reduce environmental risk, and improve future cash-flow prospects, rather than on contemporaneous energy cost burdens that may be volatile or easily passed on to consumers.

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are recommended: Management of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria should prioritize investments in green energy-efficient technologies and processes such as wind, solar, hydropower, and geothermal instead of fossil fuels (coal, oil, natural gas), as improvements in energy efficiency have been shown to enhance firm value. Moreover, firms must increase the proportion of green energy in their energy mix by adopting renewable energy sources and cleaner production methods, as this signals long-term sustainability and value creation to investors. Policymakers and industry regulators must continue to adopt strategies that can strengthen incentives and supportive frameworks that encourage green energy adoption at moderate cost, while firms should focus less on short-term energy cost management and more on strategic energy efficiency and sustainability initiatives that drive long-term firm value. There is a need to strengthen incentives and regulatory frameworks that encourage the adoption of renewable energy. Investors are advised to consider green energy efficiency indicators when evaluating firm value and long-term prospects. Finally, the study recommends that the management of listed industrial goods firms in Nigeria should align their energy efficiency and green energy initiatives with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030, particularly SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and SDG 13 (Climate Action), by investing in clean, efficient energy systems that promote sustainable industrial growth and long-term firm value.

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